

THE IMPACT ROLE AND DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The written article expresses the notion of the enhancing of tourism for foreign languages. Tourism and language are connected with each other. Without language tourism cannot show the prosperity of the world and the same tourism without language. This article is dedicated to the topic of tourism in higher education and its role. Higher education for the development of the tourism industry as one of the leading sectors, creative potential and organizational methods, the ability to analyze situations, can predict the results of work, the ability to imitate leading tourism companies, make unusual and effective decisions*

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All activities as a result of people's travelling alone or in a group with several purposes, apart from settling down and making money is in one word can be called tourism. As a system, tourism includes activities prior to trips, during the trip, or activities relating to the upstream and downstream linkages as well as the use of facilities and necessary infrastructure [Pitana, 2006:7]. The word itself derived from Sanskrit word which is "pariwisata". Dividing into two parts its meaning can be decoded in which "Pari" means all, whole, or full, and "wisata" means trip, or travel (Pambudi, 1998: 7). So, etimologically, this term relates to the meaning of trip and travel to recreate. In some areas this sector of tourism can improve living standards of residents and can open places for employment opportunities. Considering this, developing tourism and language aspects along with it which can even more enhances working opportunities.

The development of tourism as one of the branches of the industry, the modernization of the educational process, which prepares specialists with creative potential and organizational methods, the ability to analyze situations, predict the results of work, the ability to imitate leading tourism companies, make unusual and effective decisions, and the ability to know foreign languages created the need [2].

Intercultural communication, which is an important component of the professional competence of tourism managers, was tasked with finding approaches to foreign language teaching in higher education institutions that meet the changing needs of society. That is, in higher education organizations, the main focus is on helping students develop their professional knowledge and skills, and on teaching them culture, customs and traditions in communication with representatives of other countries [5].

Traditional approaches to the professional training of specialists for the tourism industry do not meet the social requirements of the specialist society, who successfully perform professional tasks in the context of intercultural interaction. In order to be considered a specialist in the field of tourism, it is not enough to know only lexical units and grammatical rules. It is important that theoretical knowledge is supplemented with practical skills and competencies. [5].

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The need to improve the socio-cultural competences of tourism students and the lack of the necessary methodology based on professionally oriented situations of communication in a foreign language created the need to improve these competences [5].

In each society, the goal of personal development is determined, and a pedagogical system should be created in accordance with it. Tourism is a system of relations that includes tourism organizations and territories that interact with the external environment. In tourism, a system is understood as a set and integrity of relations and events in the tourism network [1].

The goal of improving socio-cultural competences for students of the "Tourism" field is to acquire values as a means of professional communication [1]. During the period of study, students should be given an opportunity to involve themselves into tourism atmosphere by enabling them to travel and meet tourists in tourist sights and points in the city where it is common to see them.

According to L.V. Makar [2], "professionally oriented communication is the main condition for the existence of the international professional community, and the integration of young generations into it determines, first of all, the type of communication aimed at the transfer, storage, and exchange of information of professional importance. is reproduced, while mutual knowledge and understanding between partners play an important role in the exchange process" [1].

Imitation of scientific sources, while teaching foreign language teaching experience to non-linguistic students, it became clear that it is necessary to generalize personal teaching experience to students studying in the field of "Tourism", to improve intercultural professional competence with the help of innovative systems. The specified systems reflect the specific features of teaching a foreign language to specialists in the field of "Tourism". They determine and implement the training content, strategy, and work forms

A foreign language is not only communicative, intercultural, but also a means of forming a number of professional competencies necessary for a specialist in the field of tourism. It forms teamwork, analytical, creative, reflective abilities and skills, self-management skills, and information skills. Also, students learn to work with documents, interpret data in graphs, tables, diagrams. Competences necessary for conducting negotiations with representatives of different cultures, conducting presentations for special target audiences are formed, serve to plan and implement projects. The procedure is carried out on the basis of the following principles according to Ana Maria MIHALI, Assist. Ph.D. candidate Faculty of Marketing and International Affairs, Spiru Haret University:

- the pre-negotiation stage takes place in the preparatory phase, when the first contacts are established, data are gathered, the motivation for the future negotiation is outlined;
- the actual negotiation stage comprises the beginning, the development and the conclusion of the negotiations through an agreement of the stakeholders;
- the post-negotiation stage occurs after the signature of the agreement, when this starts taking effect and when action is taken to settle the disputes between the parties;
- the proto-negotiation stage takes places after the conclusion of the contractual terms agreed upon during the last negotiation; it marks the moment when a new negotiation process may begin, with a new pre-negotiation phase.

T.A. Nosova [4], analyzing the main goal of the educational process at the University of Tourism, distinguished three levels of educational interaction between students and the teacher:

1. individual
2. interpersonal
3. social and personal

These interaction levels are distinguished with their peculiarities of teaching and they can be involved in tourism study in which they are considered initial and primary steps to teach intercultural aspects.

According to the author, moral and spiritual qualities belong to the third level. T.A. Nosova [4] emphasizes the importance of educating patriotism, striving for social unity, developing aesthetic taste, strengthening family values, forming a positive attitude to work, educating tolerance and taking care of health [4]. As a conclusion, Tourism can impact positively in education and its development among students.

In conclusion, concerning what has been discussed above it can be inferred that the field of tourism and language skills are closely linked with each other by balancing both culture and travel in common and neutral language which should prevent misunderstandings. It has been clear from the discussion that tourism and language relation include culture studies and requires it from both sides.

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